

Feellustrator: A Design Tool for Ultrasound Mid-Air Haptics

Hasti Seifi
Arizona State University
Tempe, United States
hasti.seifi@asu.edu

Sean Chew
University of Copenhagen
Copenhagen, Denmark
sech@di.ku.dk

Antony James Nascè
Ultraleap
Bristol, United Kingdom
antony.nasce@ultraleap.com

William Edward Lowther
Ultraleap
Bristol, United Kingdom
william.lowther@ultraleap.com

William Frier
Ultraleap
Bristol, United Kingdom
william.frier@ultraleap.com

Kasper Hornbæk
University of Copenhagen
Copenhagen, Denmark
kash@di.ku.dk

Figure 1: Designing ultrasound mid-air haptic patterns with Feellustrator. (A) Sam wants to create haptic patterns for the audio and visual stimuli that he has received from his collaborators for a VR experience. (B) He uses Feellustrator to create an ultrasound mid-air haptic pattern and iteratively tests it by projecting the pattern onto his hand. (C) He exports and adds the ultrasound pattern to the virtual scene.

ABSTRACT

Ultrasound mid-air haptic technology provides a large space of design possibilities, as one can modulate the ultrasound intensity in a continuous 3D space at a high speed over time. Yet, the need for programming the patterns limits rapid ideation and testing of alternatives. We present Feellustrator, a graphical design tool for quickly creating and editing ultrasound mid-air haptics. With Feellustrator, one can create custom ultrasound patterns, layer or sequence them into complex effects, project them on the user's hand, and export them for use in external programs (e.g., Unity). To create the tool, we interviewed 13 designers who had from a few months to several years of experience with ultrasound, then derived a set of requirements for supporting ultrasound design. We demonstrate

the design power of Feellustrator through example applications and an evaluation with 15 participants. Then, we outline future directions for ultrasound haptic design.

CCS CONCEPTS

• **Human-centered computing** → **Haptic devices; Systems and tools for interaction design.**

KEYWORDS

ultrasound technology, mid-air haptics design tool, tool requirements, interviews

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1 INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound haptic technology introduces a myriad of possibilities for mid-air physical interactions. Compared to the 50–300Hz frequencies delivered by vibrotactile actuators, ultrasound technology can create spatio-temporal patterns by modulating a focal point's amplitude and position in continuous 3D space at 40kHz. Furthermore, ultrasound feedback can be rendered on the user's body and dynamically adjusted to their movements from a distance, removing the need for wearing or contacting a physical device.

Recent studies have investigated applications of ultrasound haptics, ranging from tactons [42] over mid-air interfaces for automotive or public displays [2, 16, 49] to interactions with objects and people in virtual or augmented reality environments [7, 28, 48]. Particularly, ultrasound feedback can improve the user's reaction time and the sense of agency with mid-air widgets [7, 32]. In addition, the feedback contributes to the user immersion and experience in interacting with virtual objects [31, 51] and avatars [48].

Despite the growing interest in the technology, rapid exploration and editing of ultrasound patterns is a challenge. To create with ultrasound, one needs to program haptic patterns and master its large engineering parameter space. Quick prototyping is essential for haptic design where one needs to identify salient patterns in a large space of possibilities without concrete quality metrics, yet current ultrasound tools impede this. Graphical authoring tools have been shown to improve design efficiency and outcomes for contact-based haptic technologies (e.g., vibrotactile, force feedback) [44, 45, 58]. However, they cannot be easily repurposed for ultrasound design due to differences in their rendering parameters and approach [40]. Authoring feedback for interactions in 3D space, adapting to the user body and movement, and integrating haptics with other media (e.g., in extended realities) further complicates ultrasound haptic design. These factors pose a high barrier to entry and limit rapid design exploration.

To address these limitations, we present Feellustrator, a graphical design tool for ultrasound haptics (Figure 1). The tool aims to provide a low entry threshold for ultrasound novices and support detailed control and complex stimuli design (i.e., a high ceiling) for experienced haptic designers. With Feellustrator, one can rapidly create custom patterns on a 2D canvas, time their rendering, and position them in relation to 3D user hand movements. Designers can see a visual preview and feel the ultrasound pattern, import reference visual or auditory stimuli, layer or sequence multiple patterns to create complex effects, and export their designs to use them in external programs (e.g., Unity, C# scripts).

To create Feellustrator, we interviewed 13 designers about their current practices and challenges. The designers represented a diverse sample, having from 4 months to over 10 years of ultrasound design experience. All the participants found the design space of ultrasound haptics complex, requiring extensive trial and error to find perceptually salient sensations. Programming and debugging the patterns were major roadblocks for those without a technical background, regardless of their years of ultrasound design experience. They often discarded ideas that seemed challenging to implement and adapted their design to use available preset patterns. To create more complex patterns, they had to write scripts to sequence pre-built sensations or adapt their rendering parameters according

to user movement. From these results, we derive a set of requirements for ultrasound design tools and present an implementation of them with Feellustrator. Finally, following common practices in HCI tool literature [24], we demonstrate how Feellustrator can support both novice and experienced designers with three example application scenarios and report a user study with 5 lay users and 10 ultrasound designers to assess Feellustrator with respect to its design objectives of low entry threshold and high design control. The participants found the tool intuitive and useful for rapid prototyping and refinement, conveying spatial information, and getting feedback from others. Our contributions include:

- Feellustrator, a graphical design tool for ultrasound mid-air haptics
- A set of requirements for ultrasound mid-air design tools, and data on existing design practices and challenges
- Three example scenarios showcasing the low threshold and high ceiling of Feellustrator for designers
- Results of an evaluation with 15 users suggesting Feellustrator's utility for both lay and experienced designers

2 RELATED WORK

We present past research on ultrasound haptics and summarize progress in defining the haptic design process and tools.

2.1 Parameter Space for Ultrasound Mid-Air Haptics

Ultrasound technology offers a range of parameters for creating haptic patterns. The basic unit of ultrasound rendering is a focal point that can be generated in mid-air by focusing ultrasound waves from an array of emitters [19]. Designers can vary the rendering parameters of this focal point to create various haptic patterns over time and space. For example, one can modulate the amplitude of the focal point in the 5-1000 Hz frequency range (i.e., amplitude modulation) [17] or move it along an arbitrary path at different speeds and step sizes (i.e., spatio-temporal modulation) [11, 12]. With the technology's high update rate [18, 20], one can program the focal point to move rapidly along the path, creating the perception of a *static* shape. Alternatively, the focal point can move slowly to simulate a *dynamic* pointer on the skin [15]. Similarly, while the technology can create multiple focal points at once, the high update rate of ultrasound devices means that spatio-temporal modulation of a single focal point can effectively create the illusion of multiple points. The combination of these parameters creates a large space of design possibilities that are currently hard to imagine and rapidly explore, especially for non-programmers.

Past research has shown that these rendering parameters and their interactions can influence user perception and experience. For example, Frier et al. showed that the perceived intensity of a 2D pattern (e.g., a circle) can change with its size and update rate [12] as well as the traversal speed of the focal point [11]. In another study, user confidence and performance when recognizing 2D shapes increased when the focal point moved slowly and paused (e.g., for 300 ms) at the corners of polygons [15]. Others showed that the rendering parameters of ultrasound can influence user language and associations for the haptic sensations [8, 35, 36]. Simple geometric shapes such as circles were shown to induce a range of sensations

when varying their sizes and the transversal speed of the focal point [1]. In addition, complex animated patterns could express elaborated concepts in science communication [14] and automotive contexts [2].

Ultrasound studies have mainly targeted the palm due to its high tactile sensitivity [23]. Nevertheless, recent papers have started examining other body parts such as the forearm [39], face [13], and mouth [51] for ultrasound design. The complex interactions of the ultrasound parameters and their impact on user perception further complicate ultrasound haptic design. We propose a graphical tool that allows designers to rapidly explore different parameter combinations and choose appropriate parameter values for their applications.

2.2 Haptic Design Process and Tools

Haptic experience design (HaXD) is a growing subfield of interaction design. Recent studies have outlined the main design activities and challenges of novice [47] and expert designers [43] with contact haptic technologies. The design of haptic content often involves browsing existing physical stimuli, quickly sketching alternative designs, refining a subset iteratively, and sharing the stimuli with other designers and users [27]. These studies suggested that while expert designers prioritize prototyping a range of ideas and integrating haptics with other modalities [43], novices often skimp or struggle with these activities [47]. Building on these efforts, we interview ultrasound designers with a range of expertise levels to understand their current practices and challenges. While previous work mainly focused on the design process with contact-based haptics, our work contributes a record of design with contactless technology.

Parallel to defining HaXD, the haptic tool ecosystem has also been growing. One of the earliest examples was the CHAI3D software development kit (SDK) for grounded force-feedback devices [6]. Other SDKs supported designing for do-it-yourself force-feedback [47] and ultrasound haptics [54]. Compared to SDKs, graphical design tools could offer a lower entry barrier for non-programmers. Swindells et al. presented a graphical tool for authoring tactons for a force-feedback knob [52]. Additionally, several design tools have been proposed for creating vibrotactile patterns with a single [25, 45, 46] or an array of actuators [37, 38, 44, 58]. With these tools, designers can create a haptic pattern by directly manipulating waveforms of individual actuators through a visual editor. The Tactile Animation tool [44] relies on the tactile apparent motion illusion [22] to render the sensation of movement by activating two or more vibration actuators in a special pattern on a custom haptic seat. Controlling individual actuators and using apparent tactile motion illusion are effective rendering mechanisms for contact-based haptics where the stimulation points are fixed in space, but their utility is unclear for ultrasound design. The TECHTILE toolkit [33], Voodle [29], and Weirding Haptics [9] allow designers to convert audio stimuli into force or vibration patterns. These tools further highlight the importance of rapid prototyping and feedback in haptic ideation and collaboration among designers. The haptic tool literature has also shown the utility of existing haptic examples and reference stimuli for design. When authoring vibrations with

Macaron, designers often started from existing vibration examples and modified them into new patterns [46].

In recent years, several tools have been developed for ultrasound mid-air haptics. The commercial devices by Ultraleap Ltd [54] come with an SDK in both C# and C++ for controlling the hardware. Also, the company provides a library of example patterns with pre-defined control parameters (e.g., circle radius). Designers can browse these patterns through a graphical interface (aka *Sensation Editor*) and adjust their parameters [53]. The Sensation Editor allows designers to preview the examples, but options to modify patterns are very limited. Also, the tool does not support chaining or otherwise combining the patterns, nor exporting them for use in external programs. To support the integration of ultrasound mid-air haptics with Unity, the company provides a plugin known as the Unity Core asset (UCA) [55]. Similar to the Sensation Editor, designers can access a library of existing patterns and tweak their pre-defined parameters. Both the Sensation Editor and UCA allow novices to get familiar with the technology and its possibilities, but neither can be used to define custom patterns nor control rendering beyond the pre-defined customization options. DOLPHIN is a recent framework and graphical tool for ultrasound studies [34]. Researchers can select from a set of geometrical primitives (e.g., line, arc) and vary their rendering parameters (e.g., sampling rate, curvature). DOLPHIN prioritizes systematic control of the parameters for psychophysics studies. Creating custom shapes and animations as well as body tracking are not currently supported by the tool. Finally, ultrasound researchers have developed combinations of hardware and software toolkits for defining acoustic traps and moving small particles using custom arrays of ultrasound emitters [30]. Their contribution is precise control of the pressure field rather than supporting the creation of a wide variety of haptic stimuli. We interview ultrasound designers to understand their practices with the existing tools, and we present Feellustrator to address the design challenges and tool requirements for this growing area of haptics.

3 INTERVIEWS WITH ULTRASOUND DESIGNERS

To identify avenues for supporting ultrasound designers, we sought to understand their current practices and bottlenecks. We decided to use semi-structured interviews with a diverse set of designers to collect rich qualitative data about existing ultrasound design practices and needs. The interview results led to a set of requirements for ultrasound design tools and informed the creation of Feellustrator, its demonstration scenarios, and the user evaluation (Figure 2).

Participants. We recruited 13 participants through snowball sampling, in order to include designers with a range of backgrounds and ultrasound experience. The main eligibility criterion was that the participants must have completed at least one project (e.g., M.Sc. thesis, research paper) with ultrasound technology in the past. Their participation was voluntary and they did not receive any compensation.

Procedure. We ran semi-structured interviews with individual participants via video calls over Zoom after obtaining their informed consent. After describing the goal of the interview, we

Figure 2: The stages of our design process for Feellustrator and their outcomes. We conducted a semi-structured interview with designers to identify their current practices and tool requirements, developed Feellustrator to fulfill these requirements, used the tool to demonstrate example design scenarios, and evaluated Feellustrator with lay users and ultrasound designers.

asked participants about their backgrounds and years of haptics experience. Next, we invited them to think about a recently completed project with ultrasound technology. Participants described the goal of the project, their initial ideas for their target haptic experience, and how their design evolved over the course of the project. We also asked them to describe the tools they used for creating their ultrasound experiences, and any challenges they faced with ultrasound haptics. The participants were then encouraged to share their screen and show the tools they used for their haptic design process; twelve chose to do so. After that, we invited them to describe or sketch the ideal tool for supporting their work. Before the end of the interview, they were given an opportunity to mention any remaining comments or ask questions. The interviews took between 34-77 minutes. The length of the interviews varied depending on how long it took the participant to open and share their tools and the amount of clarifications and follow-up questions from the interviewer. All the sessions were video-recorded.

Analysis. The audio recordings for all the interviews were transcribed with the Otter.ai online interface and subsequently edited for correctness. To analyse the transcripts, we used thematic analysis inspired by the Braun and Clarke’s approach [4]. Specifically, we acknowledge the active role of the researchers in generating the themes from the data and the inherent subjectivity of our analysis method. Two authors analyzed each transcript on a line-by-line basis, applying open coding to capture and generate patterns from the data. They wrote memos to describe and interpret the relationship between their codes and across the interviews. Video recordings of the interviews were re-watched as needed (e.g., when the participants showed their current tools). After open coding two transcripts, the two authors met and discussed their codes before continuing with the rest. Through this process, they aggregated codes or added new ones iteratively. The coders separately generated and drafted a set of themes and requirements for the tool, which they later merged and revised with discussion into two themes. No formula or concrete guideline exists on the number of themes in thematic analysis. The number and structure of the themes depend on several factors including the data, the research question, and the length

of the report [4, 5]. About 1-3 themes are common for a study of this size. We present the refined themes and requirements from this analysis in the next section.

4 INTERVIEW RESULTS

After summarizing the participants’ backgrounds and projects, we report two themes around their design practices and challenges, followed by the ultrasound tool requirements from the interviews.

4.1 Summary of The Participants’ Backgrounds and Design Projects

The participants had diverse backgrounds and levels of expertise in ultrasound design. They were based in eight countries across Europe and North America. Their backgrounds were rooted in computer science ($n=7$ participants), engineering ($n=3$), and psychology or arts ($n=3$). Ten participants worked in academic environments and three were employed in the industry. Their experience in ultrasound haptics also varied. Five participants had between 4 months to 1 year of experience designing with the technology, four people reported 1-2 years of experience, and the remaining four had worked with ultrasound mid-air haptics for 3-10 years.

The participants described a variety of projects with ultrasound technology, ranging from studying human perception to adding haptics to end-user applications. Specifically, five projects examined the impact of rendering parameters on user perception of movement, curvature, 2D geometric shapes, or the English alphabet on the palm. Two projects surrounded representing and modulating user emotion through ultrasound haptic patterns, whereas two others assessed the potential of ultrasound feedback for guiding user hand movement and for providing contactless UI feedback to surgeons in the operating room. In addition, four projects revolved around virtual reality (VR), three of which focused on adding haptics to interactions with 3D data, augmenting a virtual art experience with haptics, and facilitating programming by demonstration of a virtual robot. The last project investigated if congruency between the visual and haptic representations of 3D shapes in VR can influence

user recognition of the shape. All the projects focused on ultrasound feedback on the palm, except for one project where users' feet were stimulated. All participants used the Ultraleap commercial devices. None of them had altered the ultrasound hardware, except for mounting it on different platforms for their user study or target applications.

The designers used various workflows and software tools in their projects. Twelve participants had tried the example patterns in the Sensation Editor or the Unity Core Assets by Ultraleap at the start to get a feel for the technology or for ideation. To create the patterns, five participants used the example patterns from Ultraleap and either directly included them in their Unity projects or wrote a C++ or Python script to modify the example patterns in Unity. Others directly programmed the ultrasound patterns from scratch in Python notebooks or Visual Studio C++ (n=7). Two participants used both Python and C++ for various tasks in their projects. Four participants exported CSV files from their codes to use the patterns in an experiment or integrate it with other media (e.g., video).

4.2 Current Ultrasound Design Practices and Challenges

Theme 1. Ultrasound design space is complex with many unknowns, requiring extensive trial and error. The participants found the design space of ultrasound patterns larger than other haptic technologies and experienced a steep learning curve in understanding the many ultrasound rendering parameters and their interactions. As P9 noted: *"The fundamental working concept of ultrasonic... how they use it to render, how all of it work together to render one point, ah, and speed... there are so many different elements to it."*

Another challenge was the weak perceived intensity of the ultrasound, which determined if the patterns were recognized by users. The amplitude of the ultrasound focal point did not provide much design range; only 4 out of 13 participants manipulated the amplitude in their designs while others kept it at maximum. In contrast, the values of other rendering parameters directly influenced the perceived intensity of a pattern. Specifically, the size of the pattern, its duration, traversal speed of the focal point (aka draw frequency), and its step size (aka spatial sampling frequency) could create the perception of a more or less intense pattern. The design task involved searching for the optimal rendering values for geometric shapes: *"We tried maybe simple shapes like squares, triangles, circles... and every time it was a challenge. (P4)"*

Others mentioned the unintuitive nature of ultrasound rendering and the lack of design resources for the technology. The naive rendering approach was often ineffective for ultrasound due to perceptual or computational limitations. *"Because if you just blatantly put it [ultrasound focal point] at every place where you want to use it, the FPS [frame per second] will drop [to] like 20 FPS, maybe in VR, and if that's like that user will not feel comfortable at all. So you have to think about optimization as well. (P6)"* Similarly, P5 and P13 mentioned that their initial idea of rendering a surface or 3D volume felt weak and/or unpleasant. The challenge was exacerbated by the lack of design resources for the technology compared to contact-based haptics: *"So there's just a lot of quite general haptics knowledge about good vibrotactile design, and we don't have that for ultrasound haptics*

yet...(P2)" The less experienced designers (e.g., P9, P10, P13) also struggled to find good tutorials or developer forums for ultrasound design.

Instead, the participants heavily relied on trial and error or their tacit knowledge. With 4+ years of experience, P11 had *"an intuitive understanding of what ranges work for what type of sensation"*. Those with less experience looked into the default values of existing example sensations from Ultraleap. Everyone engaged for hours to days in trial and error with parameter values, a process that was disturbed when a tool or API failed to expose all the ultrasound parameters. e.g., P6 and P5 did not realize that certain parameters existed since they were missing from the example sensations.

A visual preview of the haptic patterns was essential for this design exploration. When programming and debugging patterns, the participants found it difficult to rely on their sense of touch to verify if the patterns were properly rendered on the device. Others visualized haptic patterns for exploring or communicating design ideas independently from the device. P2 and P10 initially explored ideas with pen and paper or graphic design tools such as Figma before deciding what parameters to manipulate and communicating the design to others. P7, P8, and P9 plotted their patterns in Python to *"quickly see if it's good or not without actually connecting device"*. The participants acknowledged this visual representation did not accurately reflect what was felt by users but provided *"a very good first draft (P8)"*. As a more realistic visualization, P3 and P12 used a plot or a graphical simulation of the pressure field from the ultrasound emitters.

Theme 2. Existing tools limit design exploration. In spite of the differences in the participant backgrounds, a common sentiment emerged: being restricted in exploring their haptic visions due to the narrow affordances of existing tools. All the participants engaged in some form of programming to accomplish their goals. Seven participants only used Ultraleap's programming SDK to design haptic patterns. The remaining six used scripts in Unity, C++, or C# to customize the example sensations provided by the company or create new sensations. Regardless of the approach they used, they mentioned abandoning design ideas since it seemed challenging to realize with existing software (n=7), contacting those with more experience for help (n=4), and/or adapting their design to use existing example sensations (n=10).

To expand the range of existing examples, a common approach was to change the rendering parameters of the examples at run time. A particular example was creating 3D volumes from 2D shapes. P2, P6, and P10 created 3D haptic volumes by writing scripts that modified the diameter of 2D shape examples according to the user's hand height, noting that *"all 3d shapes are just 2d shapes (P10)"*.

Another approach was to combine existing examples in a sequence or layers. P13 sequenced three ovals with different diameters to resemble a moving pressure area. P6 noted that all their designs were variations of existing ones. While this approach allowed the participants to create richer patterns, they were also limiting. *"We had to be really creative because we didn't have the freedom of just like sketching sensation... We had blocks, like blocks of just single points, blocks of circles... And we had to sort of put it together as best as we can to resemble our design. (P1)"*

Interestingly, even the more experienced participants with 3+ years of background in ultrasound (n=4) noted that programming

the patterns was a major roadblock in their work (P1, P4). With 10 years of ultrasound experience, P2 pointed: *“Other challenges, I guess, is just making sure that the experience that I’ve designed translates into code correctly.”* In several cases, the participants had to spread their work across multiple software or programming languages. P4 used Python to explore variations of a sensation, and later switched to C# after figuring out the final design. P13 wrote Python scripts for creating new sensations, prepared C# scripts for integrating them with other VR elements, and edited the effect parameters in Unity. *“We have to work something in Python, then we have to work something in C#, and we have to work in the Unity GUI and it’s a big mess to have to wrap your head around all of this. (P13)”*

Some participants had started developing custom frameworks or software to facilitate ultrasound design for themselves or others. P13 used a secondary Unity project for design exploration and later integrated it into their main Unity environment. P2 had a code template that they always copied when starting new projects. Also, P3 and P11 had developed a graphical tool for creating stimuli for their psychophysics studies. Nine participants mentioned that they had felt the need for a graphical tool in their project(s) but also noted the challenge in designing such a tool.

4.3 Requirements for the Design Tool

Table 1 shows a summary of the tool requirements that we derived from the interviews. The participants wanted a design tool that did not require programming or math knowledge and could facilitate learning of ultrasound haptic parameters. Specifically, they wanted the tool to provide them with access to all the ultrasound rendering parameters (R1) and have a library of example patterns with good default parameter values (R2). They desired a graphical tool where they could quickly create geometric shapes (R3) similar to how they used 2D graphic design software (e.g., Adobe Illustrator or Photoshop). Alternatively, they mentioned using free-form drawing together with a direct manipulation approach. *“You might even imagine that you can click with the mouse and try to move things a bit (P10)”*. Besides 2D shapes, the participants wanted a means of specifying 3D shapes during design, while acknowledging that the user would feel the shapes as 2D patterns during the interaction. P10 and P11 noted that the designer may want to switch between 2D and 3D design modes (R3). They wanted to test many timing variations of the shapes (R4) and to anchor the pattern to different positions on the hand (e.g., fingers, palm) or other body parts (e.g., foot) during design (R5).

The participants either alluded to or explicitly mentioned the need for organizing the haptic patterns into layers and sequencing them in time (R6). P12 wanted to use layering to nest stimuli into complex effects and P6 mentioned overlaying patterns in photo editing tools such as Adobe Photoshop. For sequencing, P4, P12, and P13 drew comparisons to Unity and video editing tools such as Adobe Premiere Pro that featured timelines and keyframes.

Several participants noted the importance of a visual preview for creating and debugging patterns (R7) and praised the dynamic visualization of the patterns in Ultraleap’s Sensation Editor. Interestingly, a static visualization of the haptic patterns could also

support design, as saving the rendering time mattered to the participants. For example, P7 wanted quick visual feedback and mentioned lengthy rendering time as the main reason for ignoring a visualization. P3, P7, P8, and P9 programmed 2D static plots of the patterns, depicting time progression with color or imagining it in their head. Finally, a visual preview could allow for design exploration without the need for accessing the ultrasound device (R8), something that was not available to the participants at all times (n=3).

The participants either explicitly or implicitly mentioned saving, loading, and editing the patterns in multiple sessions (R9). A human-readable file format for saving the patterns allows the designers to learn the structure of the patterns or modify them in external software if needed. In fact, several participants noted that they looked into the script files for example patterns from Ultraleap to learn how to program custom patterns (n=5).

Linking haptics to other modalities could help different stages of the design. While not explicitly requested, accessing visual or audio stimuli during design was valuable (R10). P2 and P13 noted that they often drew their ultrasound patterns on a graphical representation of the target body part. A design tool could support this practice by letting the designers import an image of the body part as a context for their design. Others mentioned referencing or integrating haptics with visual or audio stimuli and iterating over haptics (n=6). We conjectured that importing reference visual or audio files could provide a design context and facilitate later integration with other modalities. Exporting and using the stimuli in external software or code was essential after creating the patterns (R11). In most cases, this meant playing haptic patterns as part of user studies or VR interactions. In a few cases, the participants preferred scripting some parts of the design: *“Some more advanced patterns may be easier to do with the code. So you can start with the graphs and drawings, get some blueprints, and finish it later with the software. It would be nice. (P7)”*

The participants also noted several features that were nice to have but not essential (R12). They sought automatic checks on units and range of values (P7) as well as using formulas (n=3) or free-form drawings to quickly create complex effects (n=4). Some participants referred to replicating the patterns in space or time (n=2) or showed a simulation of the ultrasound pressure in other software tools (n=2). Others noted the design tool should highlight potential issues with a design (P8) or suggest alternative patterns (P9). Adjusting parameters of the stimuli (e.g., size) in external programs was appreciated (n=4), especially for displaying the pattern on different hand or body sizes, but it was deemed secondary.

In the following sections, we refer to the tool requirements using their numbers in Table 1.

5 FEELLUSTRATOR: THE DESIGN TOOL

Based on the identified tool requirements, we developed Feellustrator, a design tool for ultrasound mid-air haptics. The majority of the participants in the interviews emphasized the importance of 2D design, calling 3D design as an extension of 2D patterns. Feellustrator allows designers to create a wide variety of 2D patterns and project them to the user body in 3D space. To manage scope, we leave the creation of 3D volumes to future work. Furthermore, since the majority of the participants used Ultraleap’s STRATOS

Requirement Category	Description
R1. Accessing and manipulating all design parameters	Control the pattern's position, amplitude, start time, duration, amplitude modulation frequency, draw frequency, spatial sampling rate, and size
R2. Accessing a library of patterns	Provide a set of example patterns including basic 2D and 3D shapes and animation effects (e.g., expanding circle). Set default rendering parameters to reflect best practices from the literature.
R3. Specifying the spatial pattern	Support designing custom patterns by specifying the key points and their connections. Enable switching between 2D and 3D views.
R4. Specifying temporal progress	Provide control over the start time and duration for a single key point as well as a group of points. Allow control of draw frequency (i.e., traversal speed of the focal point) for a group of key points and their connections.
R5. Positioning the pattern	Allow projecting the pattern to a fixed 3D position or anchoring it to the user's body (e.g., palm, fingers) using motion tracking hardware
R6. Layering and Sequencing	Support organizing multiple patterns by sequencing them in time and/or layering them over each other in space.
R7. Rendering a Visual Preview	Provide a static preview of the design range offered by the device and the spatio-temporal pattern and a dynamic rendering of the pattern that reflects the focal point movement speed and spatial sampling rate.
R8. Designing w/o hardware	Create and preview the patterns without connecting to the ultrasound hardware
R9. Importing Reference Visual and Audio Stimuli	Add custom images (e.g., of a target body part or visual stimuli) or audio files as a reference or context for the ultrasound pattern
R10. Saving, Loading, and Editing	Save designs in a human-readable and editable format (e.g., JSON), load and edit them over multiple sessions
R11. Exporting and Using	Output the pattern in a format that can be integrated into external scripts (Python or C#) or software (e.g., Unity).
R12. Nice to haves	Features that can improve designer performance and experience or enhance the tool's usability
(A) Automatic checks	Fix range of parameters to valid values, automatically check for SDK updates and dependencies
(B) Using formulas	Define patterns with a mathematical formula
(C) Drawing	Create the patterns with free-form drawing
(D) Replicating	support copy/paste
(E) Simulating output	Provide a simulation of the pressure field or its perceived intensity
(F) Recommending designs	Suggest alternative temporal renderings for the spatial patterns, highlight potential flaws in a pattern (e.g., using heuristics)
(G) Adapting in use	Adjust the rendering parameters of a pattern (especially size, duration, and draw frequency) during use (e.g., in external code or Unity)

Table 1: Requirements for ultrasound design tools

Explore device, the current version of Feellustrator supports integration with that device. Other ultrasound devices can be linked to Feellustrator by implementing the relevant functions for the devices' SDKs. Feellustrator is available for download and use at this address: <https://hastiseifi.com/research/feellustrator/>

Feellustrator has the following main components as shown in Figure 3: (A) a library of examples, (B-C) a canvas and a timeline for creating and timing custom spatio-temporal patterns, (D) panels for controlling the design parameters as well as the layering and sequencing functionalities, and (E-F) toolbars for linking to the hardware, performing file operations, and controlling the playback settings. These components support the requirements R1-R11 as well as R12.A and R12.B. Below, we describe each component and how they fulfill these tool requirements.

5.1 Accessing a Library of Examples (R1, R2)

Designers can get started quickly with the 10 example ultrasound patterns including simple geometric shapes and animated patterns in the *library* (Figure 3-A). When clicking on an example, its spatial and temporal structure and design parameters are presented in Feellustrator *canvas* and *timeline* (Figure 3-B,C). The designer can check the example's default settings, adjust them, and access their custom-created patterns in this library.

5.2 Creating and Timing Custom Spatio-Temporal Patterns and Positioning Them (R3, R4, R5)

With the canvas, the designers can define custom geometric paths similar to Adobe Illustrator (R3). The canvas provides a 2D preview of the recommended rendering space afforded by the external hardware. In our implementation, the canvas is centered around the reference position of the device (0,0) and goes from -10cm to 10cm in both X and Y directions. The graph paper background and the placement settings accessible from the top right corner of the canvas in Figure 3 allow accurate positioning of the pattern in three dimensions (R5). Specifically, the designer can either connect the pattern to track key positions on the hand (e.g., palm center, index finger) in 3D space or they can fix the pattern to a custom position on all three axes (x, y, z). The designer can click on the canvas to define a custom path for the ultrasound focal point as a series of *spatial nodes*. The nodes can be moved or deleted on the canvas.

The total duration of the pattern and the time taken to travel from one node to another can be defined on a *timeline* below the canvas (R4). On the timeline, designers can add *intensity keyframes* to adjust the amplitude of the focal point through the pattern duration. The number of intensity keyframes can be equal or different to the number of spatial nodes to allow further design freedom.

Figure 3: Feellustrator and its main components: (A) a library of examples, (B) a canvas for creating custom spatial patterns and positioning settings at the top right corner, clicking on it opens a pop-up modal shown on the side, (C) a timeline for the pattern duration and timing as well as the ultrasound amplitude over time, (D) panels for controlling the design parameters of the patterns as well as layering and sequencing them, (E-F) toolbars for hardware control, file operations, and pattern playback.

The designers can specify the number of repetitions over the path and other playback options using the dedicated toolbar below the timeline (Figure 3-F).

5.3 Accessing Design Parameters, Layering, and Sequencing Patterns (R1, R6, R12)

Feellustrator has four panels on the right side (Figure 4), providing access to the ultrasound design parameters (R1) as well as the layering and sequencing functionalities (R6). These panels are called: *Brush*, *Node*, *Intensity*, and *Sequence*.

On the *Brush* panel (Figure 4-a), they can select or design a second pattern to layer and move over the path that they defined on the canvas. One can think of this layered pattern as a *tactile brush* that moves over the path in the canvas to create a complex effect. Feellustrator has a set of default brush primitives (e.g. circle and line) which can be selected on this panel and re-sized through a slider. For the default brushes, their design parameters are set and automatically adjusted to match the recommendations from the literature (e.g., [11]). Thus, a novice designer can quickly use and resize the brushes with little prior knowledge. Experienced ultrasound designers can define a custom brush using a formula (R12.B). Feellustrator currently supports creation of parametric curved brushes using the formulas for lissajou and rose curves. Lissajou and rose are two standard families of periodic curves in mathematics that can create a wide variety of shapes (see Figure 4(a) for an example).

On the other three panels, the designers can change the rendering order and parameters of the spatial nodes, adjust the ultrasound amplitude over time, and sequence patterns. On the *Node* panel, the designers can specify the exact timing and position of each spatial

node on the path in the canvas (R1). Furthermore, the brush can be rotated or scaled in X and Y directions at each node, offering more dynamism and complexity to the designers (R6). On the *Intensity* panel, they can specify the amplitude of the ultrasound for the *intensity keyframes* over the duration of the pattern (R1). Note that these keyframes are also accessible on the timeline. On the *Sequence* panel, they can sequence two or more patterns from the library and change the order or the number of repetitions for each pattern (R6). This sequencing functionality works similar to timing animations in existing software such as Microsoft PowerPoint and iOS Keynote.

5.4 Rendering a Visual Preview, Linking to Hardware, and File Operations (R7, R8, R9, R10, R11)

From the top and bottom toolbars (Figure 3-E,F), the designers can play the pattern, connect to the ultrasound and hand tracking hardware, import reference visual and audio stimuli, and finally save or export their designs.

They can see a static and a dynamic visual preview of the haptic pattern as they design (R7). The static visualization is always available on the canvas. For the dynamic visual rendering, several of the interview participants praised the visualisation from Ultraleap's Sensation Editor. Thus, we developed a similar preview within Feellustrator. This visual preview allows the designers to keep working on their designs without a device (R8).

On the *Playback* toolbar (Figure 3-F), the designers can play a pattern, import an audio file (R9), and reference the audio preview to specify the amplitude curve for the pattern duration. The tool also provides basic envelope detection functionality to automatically match the amplitude of the ultrasound to the amplitude profile of

(a) The *Brush* panel has a Primitive preset for creating a custom brush pattern, which can be layered over a spatial pattern in the canvas

(b) The *Node* panel for timing and scaling the brush at each spatial node in the canvas

(c) The *Intensity* panel for controlling the ultrasound amplitude over time

(d) The *Sequence* panel for chaining two or more patterns

Figure 4: Four side panels on Feellustrator for accessing the ultrasound design parameters and layering or sequencing patterns.

the imported audio. Similarly, the designers can import an image, scale it on the canvas, and use it as a reference to trace a spatial pattern.

On the *Menu* toolbar at the top (Figure 3-E), they can select the hand icon to activate hand tracking and the device icon to connect to the ultrasound array. After clicking the hand icon, they can see a mesh of their hand in real time on the canvas. They can anchor the position of the ultrasound pattern to the center of the hand or move it to other custom positions in relation to the hand. The designer can select the hardware icon to connect Feellustrator to a supported ultrasound device (R8) and play the pattern on the device.

When the designer saves a new pattern (R10), Feellustrator stores its parameter values in a JSON file in a dedicated “haptics” subfolder within the Feellustrator’s main folder. The human-readable format

can be accessed by the designers, edited by collaborators that do not have access to Feellustrator, or parsed by third-party tools. This format also creates smaller file sizes compared to storing all the (x,y,z) positions and amplitude values for each time sample in the pattern. Feellustrator has an Export function (R11) which writes the pattern to a JSON file. The JSON file can then be rendered into a CSV format at the desired update rate using a standalone script. This feature allows designers to adjust the update rate of the pattern based on the specifications of their target ultrasound device or use this feature to study the effect of the update rate on the user perception [12, 34]. The exported CSV format can be used in external scripts (e.g., C++) or software (e.g., Unity).

Figure 5: Alex loads the JSON file for the corner stimulus as a starting point for his design. An example design where Alex added new nodes to slow down the speed of the focal point at the corner (Stimulus D).

6 EXAMPLE DESIGN SCENARIOS

We present three example scenarios by drawing inspiration from the participants' projects and existing literature on ultrasound mid-air haptics. The scenarios show that designers can quickly create a variety of haptic patterns without the need for programming. The examples are roughly ordered according to their spatial and temporal design complexity.

6.1 Rapidly Creating Stimuli Alternatives for a Perception Study

Alex (they/them) is a psychophysics researcher who is working with their colleagues to improve user recognition of shapes. At this stage, they are prototyping a set of stimuli for a pilot study. They intend for participants to experience these stimuli at a fixed position on their palm, held 20 cm above the center of the device. Alex has received a JSON file, called "corner.json", from their colleague that contains a single corner sensation with a circle brush. They add "corner.json" to the "haptics" folder of Feellustrator, where ultrasound patterns are saved. Then, they create four alternative renderings of the pattern for their hypothesis.

Stimulus A - Static corner: Alex loads the "Corner" pattern from the library. Because the loop duration is set to 0.01 seconds, the focal point moves fast, and the pattern is felt like a static corner [15] (Figure 5).

Stimulus B - Moving pointer: Alex extends the loop duration to 1 second and feels the corner being drawn on their palm, starting from the bottom to the top and right.

Stimulus C - Size-changing pointer: Alex decides to modify the size of the circle brush on the path. They change the second node's ScaleX and ScaleY parameters from a factor of 1.0 to 2.0 on the *Node* panel, making the brush double in size at the middle node, and shrinking back to its default size at the end node.

Stimulus D - Speed-changing pointer: To slow down the brush around the corner, Alex creates two extra nodes before and after the corner. The new nodes automatically slow down the brush due to their positions. Alex could further adjust the timing of the nodes to exaggerate the speed change.

6.2 Data Physicalization on a Map

Jessie (they/them) is a data statistician who wants to use ultrasound haptics to show the current population density of two geographic regions and their predicted populations in five years. To depict the current population, they import a map of the regions as a reference image (Figure 6-a) and cluster together several nodes to increase the perceived intensity of the ultrasound (Figure 6-b). Each node represents one unit of the population (e.g., 100,000 people). Then, they create a pulsating on/off curve for the focal point's amplitude in order to prevent rendering of the ultrasound feedback when moving in between nodes (Figure 6-c). This creates the feeling of clusters rather than a moving point. After saving the first pattern, Jessie modifies the number and position of the nodes to reflect the predicted population. They change the brush preset to a line to differentiate it from the current population, and save this as a second pattern. Finally, they chain the two saved patterns in the *Sequence* panel so that the user can feel the population change in the two regions over the next 5 years (Figure 6-d).

6.3 Multimodal Effects for a Virtual Reality Scene

Sam (he/him) is an up-and-coming VR developer who has been working with ultrasound mid-air haptics for the past year. For his next project, he wants to create an artistic VR experience with mid-air haptics using Feellustrator (Figure 7). Sam's work includes two of many different VR scenes- one of a bee, and one of a sparkler. When the user places their hands over the bee or the sparkler, they should feel moving and buzzing and flower sparkle patterns on their hand respectively. Sam's goal is to create two patterns, combining visuals, sound, and ultrasound haptics. To start, he imports an audio file for his first piece. Then, he creates a spiral pattern using three nodes that are overlaid in the canvas. By changing the brush to the dial brush preset and scaling up the brush at each consecutive node, he can make the brush feel spiraling outwards. Additionally, he changes the amplitude profile to a simple spike that peaks at the loudest part of the sound effect, and goes back down to about half. After importing another audio file for the second pattern, he creates multiple nodes on the canvas, times them in the *Node* panel, and designs a custom flower-shaped brush by modifying the parameters

Figure 6: In the data physicalization example, Jessie follows the above steps to create two ultrasound patterns representing the current and future populations of two geographic regions on a map and sequences them in time.

of the lissajous and rose curve formulas in the *Brush* panel. He tests various brush sizes, uses hand tracking to center the pattern on the palm, and creates a pulsating on/off curve for the focal point’s amplitude. Finally, he exports his custom ultrasound patterns and adds them to the two VR scenes.

7 EVALUATION STUDY

We sought to evaluate Feellustrator with respect to its design goals of lowering the entry threshold for those outside the field and providing design power for ultrasound designers. Thus, we ran hands-on design and interview sessions with lay users and ultrasound designers.

7.1 Methods

Participants - We recruited 15 participants, including 5 lay users and 10 ultrasound designers. The lay users ($P1_{Lay}$ - $P5_{Lay}$) included one social worker and four university students. Two mentioned drawing digitally as a hobby, one had graphic design experience, and one had some experience with animation and VR games. None of the lay participants had any background in haptics. We included the lay users to assess if the tool can lower the entry threshold for those new to ultrasound haptics. The ultrasound designers included

four designers from the prior interview study ($P6_{Des}$ - $P9_{Des}$) and six new designers ($P10_{Des}$ - $P15_{Des}$). This approach helped us close the loop on the designer needs from the earlier interviews, and also validate the tool’s utility for the broader group of ultrasound designers. In terms of ultrasound background, three of them had between 7 months to 1 year of experience, two people had 1-2 years of experience, and five had 3-8 years of experience. The ultrasound designers had experience with Unity ($n=2$) or designing audio ($n=2$), graphics ($n=6$), or video ($n=2$) as a hobby.

Procedure - Each session involved background questions, tool demonstration, hands-on design with Feellustrator, and closing questions. The ultrasound designers participated over Zoom using their STRATOS Explore devices, while the lay users completed the session with a STRATOS Explore device in the lab. We sent installation files and instructions to the ultrasound designers before the session. After answering background questions, the experimenter demonstrated Feellustrator by either playing a video (for ultrasound designers) or providing a live demonstration (for lay users). The live interaction helped familiarize the lay users with the technology as they could feel the ultrasound patterns during the demonstration. Then, the participants completed three step-by-step warm-up design tasks to get familiar with the interface. These tasks asked

(a) Creating the spiral pattern by adding three nodes in the same position on the canvas, (b) Creating a sparkler pattern with new nodes, making a custom flower brush, positioning the pattern using hand-tracking, and pulsing the amplitude on the timeline

(c) Adding the spiral pattern to a virtual bee

(d) Adding the sparkler pattern to a virtual sparkler

Figure 7: Designing two ultrasound patterns and integrating in two virtual scenes in Unity

participants to play the default patterns in the Feellustrator’s library, modify one of them, and create a custom brush preset. The participants explored the interface on their own to complete the tasks, and the experimenter provided hints if needed. Next, the participants created ultrasound patterns for three open-ended design tasks with the prompts: (a) “create an explosion”, (b) “tell a driver to turn around”, and (c) “Think about a sensation that you’d like to create. Describe it and create it with the tool”. We selected the first two prompts to have a primarily temporal or spatial element, while the last prompt allowed for covering the participants’ design goals. The participants shared their screens and were asked to verbalize their thoughts. Finally, we asked the participants about what worked or did not work well, how they may or may not use the tool in the future, and if they had any other comments. We collected the design files from all the sessions. Each session lasted about 1 hour and was recorded using Zoom.

Analysis - The audio recordings were transcribed with Otter.ai. Two authors watched the recordings and took notes on the participant interactions with Feellustrator, and the patterns they created. One author synthesized the notes into a summary of the interactions, cross-referencing and linking them with the participant comments from the transcripts. The two authors met and discussed the results to arrive at the final summary results presented below.

7.2 Results

We summarize the participants’ interactions with Feellustrator and their comments. Overall, their interactions and comments suggest that Feellustrator can lower the entry threshold for those without ultrasound experience, support quick prototyping and refinement, and help users develop new insights about designing perceptually-salient patterns.

7.2.1 Design interactions and outcomes. All participants completed the three open-ended design tasks in less than 30 minutes. The participants realized the design tasks in a variety of ways, suggesting the design flexibility of Feellustrator. For example, $P7_{Des}$ created an “explosion” by using a spatially expanding pattern from the library and adding a few spatial nodes to create a “scattered” effect. $P13_{Des}$ imitated the feel of dropping the bomb through several vertically-separated nodes and modified the brush size and intensity at each node to create “a sudden pulse which is heavy”. In some cases, the participants aimed for similar perceptual goals but achieved them in different ways. For example, to create emphasis, the participants rotated the “line” brush ($n=2$), scaled the brush ($n=2$), overlaid two or more nodes to create a pause ($n=4$), or modified the intensity and number of loops ($n=2$). For the open prompt, the participants created a wide range of patterns such as a vortex pattern, a cat, a

warning for a car approaching from another lane, a texture, affective touch by a person, and the feel of holding a coffee mug.

Despite the limited duration of the session, all participants iteratively refined their designs and some created several alternatives. Everyone polished their designs by modifying the brush parameters, the number and position of nodes, or the timing or intensity curve. P_{14Des} created and saved three alternative designs for a “breathing sensation” in their open design task. Similarly, others created alternatives or started anew after trying their initial idea ($n=4$). Overall, the ultrasound designers focused on refining their designs for optimal user perception more than lay users. For example, for the “turn-around” pattern, eight (out of 10) designers refined the layout or parameters of the ultrasound as described above to emphasize the turn and make it easier to perceive, but none of the lay users tried to do that. We did not find any other notable difference in the design activities of the lay users and ultrasound designers.

7.2.2 Perceptual insights. With the real-time haptic and visual feedback, the participants shared spontaneous observations about ultrasound perception. While repositioning the pattern on the canvas, P_{2Lay} discovered “oh, wait... the signal is more intense here [on the finger]”, reflecting the higher density of tactile receptors on the fingers compared to the palm. Those with ultrasound experience also had new insights about ultrasound intensity. While creating a custom brush with the rose and Lissajous parameters, P_{14Des} noted: “[the pattern is] more complex [but] less intense”. P_{13Des} commented about the relationship between speed and intensity: “The short timing is not perceivable although the intensity is maximum.”

The coupling of visuals and haptics also helped user to realize any discrepancies and identify design bugs. P_{3Lay} thought the combination of visuals and haptics enabled “an accurate experience”, while P_{1Lay} and P_{7Des} commented that they could not feel the full spatial complexity of the patterns via touch. P_{11Des} could see but not feel the last segment of their pattern and subsequently resolved the design bug by correcting the intensity curve. Similarly, P_{2Lay} thought the visual component improved their haptic perception.

7.2.3 Participants’ comments. In response to our closing questions, the participants found Feellustrator easy to use and useful for exploring and sharing design ideas. The participants ($n=12$ out of 15) explicitly mentioned that the tool is intuitive, straightforward, and similar to other tools they had used. Several participants commented on the design capabilities of Feellustrator. Referring to their previous project, P_{11Des} noted that: “I think this definitely would have gotten me to create something a bit more creative. Yeah, it’d have given me a lot more to think about with the overall design as well.”

The designers found the tool useful for rapid prototyping for VR and other applications ($n=4$), conveying shape and spatial information ($n=3$), exporting stimuli for user experiments ($n=4$), and getting feedback from others ($n=2$). P_{14Des} stated: “Being able to share any stimulus you can create here and say, Hey, try this one, and send the file that’s priceless.” Being comfortable with programming, P_{8Des} noted that they would use the tool to explore and create stimuli for an experiment, but for psychophysics studies they may use programming to be completely certain about the position of the focal point. P_{12Des} thought they could ask lay users to explore haptic patterns with Feellustrator. Similarly, all the lay users found

the tool useful and shared joy and enthusiasm while using it: “I feel like there’s so many opportunities with this. (P_{4Lay})”

When asked about what did not work well with Feellustrator, the participants suggested features for further improving the tool’s efficiency and usability. The designers wanted to group and move spatial nodes ($n=2$), have more convenience functions for temporal design on the timeline such as copy/paste ($n=2$), add randomness to a pattern ($n=2$), draw with a pen ($n=2$), and customize the view by resizing or hiding the elements ($n=3$). Two participants wanted to use other hand-tracking hardware with Feellustrator ($n=2$). Finally, the participants noted adding more tooltips ($n=3$) or changing the icon, name, or location of some elements ($n=4$). These suggestions can help further polish and extend the tool’s support, but do not pose new requirements for ultrasound design.

8 DISCUSSION

We compare the ultrasound practices and challenges with the literature accounts of design for contact-based haptics, reflect on our process for designing and evaluating Feellustrator, and outline future directions.

8.1 Mid-Air Ultrasound vs. Contact-Based Haptic Design Practices and Requirements

Similarities to the contact-based haptics - Ultrasound mid-air haptic design has similar challenges and requirements to contact-based haptics. Difficulty in programming and debugging the patterns, finding design guidelines and resources, and identifying perceptually salient patterns through trial and error are also challenges for contact-based haptics. These challenges are even harder to overcome for designers due to the larger design space of ultrasound, the complex interaction of its many parameters, and the lack of established design practices for the technology. Similarly, the ultrasound tool requirements in Table 1 overlap with the requirements that previous work suggested for contact-based haptics [37, 38, 44, 52]. The main difference is the larger extent of control required in the ultrasound tool. For example, recent vibrotactile design tools [44] can render a continuous linear motion using apparent tactile motion illusion. However, the control parameters of the motion such as its length, continuity, and speed are limited by the number of vibration actuators, and thereby their interface requirements are less demanding than for ultrasound design.

Specific challenges for the ultrasound design - The more nuanced challenges and requirements of ultrasound are linked to its weak intensity, high update rate, and contactless rendering. While the technology allows updating the focal point at over 40KHz, designers should avoid moving the focal point over a large area in a short time frame since the combination of weak intensity and fast updates can lead to perceptual or computational inefficiencies. The patterns need to be aligned to a moving body part (e.g., hand) and account for how the body’s orientation can impact the perception. Regarding the requirements, the visual preview is essential during design since the weak intensity of the renderings makes verifying or debugging the patterns near impossible by touch (R7). Interestingly, the exact position of the focal point cannot be displayed and observed by our visual system at such a high update rate. Thus, the dynamic visual previews are mainly a proxy for the haptic patterns.

The preview leverages the persistence of vision to emulate what the spatiotemporal modulation may feel like. Due to the fast update rate of ultrasound, layering can have interesting variations (R6). For example, one may layer two nodes in the same place to make it feel stronger or create temporal progress similar to designing for a vibration actuator, but also with ultrasound one can layer a custom pattern (i.e., brush) to move over another pattern (scenario 3 in Section 6.3) to create nuanced effects. Integrating body tracking in the design tool and anchoring patterns to a moving body part are new requirements for contactless technology (R4).

Comparing beginners with experienced designers - The ultrasound design practices were similar for beginners and experienced designers in our interview and evaluation studies. Recent studies of novice and expert designers with contact-based haptics have shown that some challenges and design activities may differ based on the designer's expertise level. For example, Seifi et al. reported that novices spent most of their time debugging and programming the haptic device [47] whereas experts prioritized conceptual and multimodal design [43]. In the first interview study, we did not find any notable differences in the challenges and activities reported by those who were newer to ultrasound technology. The beginners (<2 years of ultrasound experience) more frequently pointed to the learning curve with existing tools but this was also echoed by some of the experienced designers such as P4 with 5 years of ultrasound experience who noted that they sometimes had to restudy the ultrasound concepts at the start of a new project. We conjecture that the severity of the reported challenges for ultrasound may depend on the level of experience with the technology, but the interview methodology did not allow us to assess this. In the evaluation study, ultrasound designers focused on refining their designs more than lay users. This observation needs to be further studied in the future, but this point may relate to the higher focus of haptics experts on refining for multisensory perception in prior work [43, 47].

8.2 Reflections and Implications for Future Work

Feellustrator's design process - We designed and built Feellustrator by following established HCI practices for requirement gathering, design, and evaluation [24, 50]. The semi-structured interviews grounded the design of Feellustrator in existing practices and the needs of ultrasound designers with a range of expertise levels. The tool requirements provided a list for our team to discuss and reason the interface choices and iterate on the choices while developing Feellustrator. Similarly, these requirements can inform the design of future ultrasound design tools and be a starting point for supporting design with other contactless technologies. Finally, the demonstration of Feellustrator through example scenarios and user evaluation are in line with established practices in the HCI toolkit research. In a recent review paper, Ledo et al. found that demonstration and user study were common approaches to evaluating HCI design tools [24]. To demonstrate a tool, common strategies include replicating existing examples and showing novel ones. We followed these practices in selecting and developing the three example scenarios. Specifically, Scenario 1 replicates the work of Hajas et al. [15], while Scenario 2 and 3 are inspired by the interviews,

but they demonstrate novel examples. Finally, the evaluation results with lay users and ultrasound designers suggest the low entry threshold and high design power of Feellustrator for ultrasound haptics.

Extending ultrasound mid-air haptics tool support - Feellustrator's design scope and features can be extended in future tools on the input, pattern creation, preview, export, and use aspects. On the input side, future tools can go beyond importing reference stimuli and allow designers to sketch ultrasound patterns with hand drawing or voice input. Such conversions have been recently proposed for force-feedback [21, 29] and vibrotactile stimuli [9]. Future work can investigate plausible mappings for ultrasound. For pattern creation, Feellustrator can be extended in three ways. First, the tool supports designing 2D patterns and projecting them in the 3D space, but does not provide library primitives or direct manipulation control for creating 3D volumes. Little work has been done to identify good rendering approaches for 3D volumes. The state-of-the-art rendering approach for 3D volumes is to render their 2D cross-section on the hand [26]. Rendering 3D shapes require considerably more computation power. Thus, future tools need to think about how best to support 3D designs. Also, allowing the designer to switch between 2D and 3D visualizations of ultrasound patterns can be useful, especially in future extensions supporting 3D designs.

Second, Feellustrator is based on a single moving focal point. This approach is the dominant rendering paradigm in ultrasound design. An alternative use of ultrasound is to create several focal points in the device workspace. Creating more than one focal point at once leads to a significant decrease in acoustic pressure and perceived strength. None of the designers in our interviews used multiple focal points in their designs, although the functionality is supported by the Ultraleap API, suggesting that this functionality is not critical in practice. Thus, we did not prioritize this feature in creating Feellustrator. However, future work can extend Feellustrator to allow creating and controlling multiple focal points, perhaps to be represented as separate tracks in the Feellustrator's timeline.

Third, body tracking and visual preview functionalities can be extended. The current version of Feellustrator only supports hand tracking from the Ultraleap device. The tool can be extended in the future to integrate with other external tracking devices such as the OptiTrack motion capture systems [57]. An alternative preview could be a simulation of ultrasound pressure based on recent efforts for simulating the ultrasound vibrations on human skin [10].

Finally, on the export and use side, future tools can allow adapting ultrasound patterns in real-time based on external triggers. Adaptive approaches to audio design have improved game creation and user experience [56]. Similarly, an ultrasound pattern can be scaled based on the user's hand size or its rendering speed can adapt to the user's movement.

Developing Perceptual Algorithms for Ultrasound Design - Future research can develop algorithms that predict or optimize for user perception of ultrasound patterns. In particular, the perceived intensity of an ultrasound pattern depends on all rendering parameters including the pattern's geometric shape and timing as well as the user's tactile sensitivity. Currently, designers rely on trial and error or their tacit knowledge to set the parameter values. Future

work can build on recent efforts in this area [41] to develop a predictive model for the perceived intensity of a pattern. Furthermore, future work can investigate perceptual algorithms for morphing one ultrasound pattern into another in a sequence [3], or identify areas of an ultrasound pattern that are suboptimal perceptually to recommend alternative renderings. Finally, haptic stimuli often needs to be integrated with other modalities [27]. Future work can investigate how to support ultrasound design in situ in virtual or augmented reality environments to further provide design context and facilitate multimodal design integration. In addition, future studies can investigate perceptual rules or heuristics that govern multimodal design and develop generative models for ultrasound haptics based on the visual and auditory stimuli for a given scenario. Such perceptual models, even if not fully accurate, can notably reduce the trial and error time and guide ultrasound mid-air pattern design.

9 CONCLUSION

Contactless haptic technologies provide a myriad of new possibilities and challenges for rendering touch sensations to the users' bodies in free space. As ultrasound mid-air haptics mature, designers need an effective means of creating with the technology. We present Feellustrator to support creative design and scientific explorations with the ultrasound technology. Furthermore, we contribute to the understanding of design challenges with this contactless technology by reporting and analysing results from semi-structured interviews. This work is a step towards a future where haptic technology can engage and immerse us in new experiences without interfering with our natural touch abilities.

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